

Navigating to the Future: Emerging Strategies and Innovations to Enrich Higher Education Effectiveness

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The emergence of technological and social expectancy, intentional actions, and real-time results have higher education institutions rapidly shifting policies, practices, and behaviors to meet the needs of their respective communities (e.g., prospective students, current students, alumni, employees, partners, and external compliance organizations). The purpose of this article is to highlight a few emerging trends that will be essential for colleges and universities to adapt to increase the quality of instruction, service, and overall sustainability and effectiveness.

Keywords— Data utilization, higher education, business intelligence, innovation, strategy, learning ecosystem, artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of technological and social expectancy, intentional actions, and real-time results have higher education institutions rapidly shifting policies, practices, and behaviors to meet the needs of their respective communities (e.g., prospective students, current students, alumni, employees, partners, and external compliance organizations). The purpose of this article is to highlight a few emerging trends that will be essential for colleges and universities to adapt to increase the quality of instruction, service, and overall effectiveness. The following sections provide snapshots of a few emerging trends and ideas that may have game-changing effects in higher education.

II. BIG DATA AND PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS

In today's data-rich environment, higher education institutions are drowning in data, thirsting for information and seeking champions for transitioning information to knowledge to action that leads to positive change. Therefore, institutions need to develop synchronous systems where data is accessible, palatable, and usable to provide relevancy in support of timely decisions and actions. While tabular information is great, it may cause analysis paralysis, similarly to many dashboards creates visualization paralysis. Institutions should develop systems that can automatically produce datasets with interpretations which can facilitate conversations.

While big data modeling is trending and many at-risk models and systems exist, there is still a need to blend real-time behavioral analytics from inside and outside of the classroom with big data from the student information system and the economic climate to determine high probability outcomes. Additionally, predictive analytics systems need to intentionally and proactively respond before adverse outcomes occur. Therefore, based on the models of blended data, systems need to automatically outreach services to address situations through a range of communication channels. This would alleviate the manual process of late reactions to model output and effectively direct students to the correct interventions.

Higher education needs to adopt and adapt data strategies similar to mobile market space, which harvests and fuses a broad

range of consumer data together to facilitate action. The goal would be to create a seamless integration and blending of data from economic, social, characteristic, and behavioral categories segmented within the geospatial map and draw inferences to academic performance outcomes. This approach would provide support to develop strategies for change. The different change antidotes can be included in the model to determine the impact of the situation. As a result, a machine learning process can be developed that will automatically outreach specific interventions based on the real-time student data. As data continues to enter into the system, the machine will learn from and transition actions to meet the demand of the future students.

Artificial intelligence (AI) will need to adopt best case scenario planning and model adaptation which is associated with best possible outcomes. This will require a set of best-case scenarios to be developed with characteristics for the machine to detect and associate situations with. Therefore, this will allow machines to make better suggestions and provide solutions to decision makers and students.

III. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI), AUGMENTED REALITY AND VIRTUAL REALITY FOR ENGAGEMENT

As institutions blend online component into courses, it would be key to adapt AI system that can search, gather, and provide relevant content into the course room based on media and literature in real-time. This would support a diversified learning experience with real-time associativity to content that complements the theoretical framework of the material covered. Additionally, to support continuous engagement, institutions need to adopt an AI infrastructure that can review and provide engaging commentary in an online environment (e.g., learning management system (LMS)) to students collaborating in discussion forums or chat sessions. This facilitation tool could open the opportunity to engage a broad range of students with regular and substantive interactions. These tools could be plug-ins for different LMS systems, thus creating universal access to the tool and decreasing the overhead cost of adoption.

To strategies to scale and continue progression into the frontier of diversified learning, institutions should explore transition physical laboratories to augmented reality or virtual experiences. Though the utilization of this technology, institutions could engage a larger scale of students in a practitioner-based environment.

IV. LEARNING ECOSYSTEMS

The theory of learning ecosystems merges course content and assignments into a structured process which proactively ties all courses together and foster directed learning through contextualization across program core course sequences and general education. The learning ecosystem should be benchmarked with competency assessments, which are presented to the student from exposure through completion to support persistence through momentum points of success.

Learning environments should be created on personal learning development models that utilize social and neuro-psychological analysis (and big data sets mentioned earlier) to provide educational roadmaps and content delivery methods that adapt to learning styles of the students. This would also account for the timeframe of learning and assessment of learning. To provide a well-rounded educational experience, institutions need to create

support infrastructures to engage prospective students through consist which would consist of integrated success teams that provide student and academic support throughout the learning ecosystem. Additionally, institutional programs need to build a partnership to aligning internship and job opportunities that support programmatic coursework to provide depth to overall learning.

V. DISCUSSION

The purpose of the article is to help facilitate discussions around emerging strategies and which would be practical to increase teaching, learning, and overall effectiveness. Through collaborative and diversified scenario impact planning, institutions can best determine new methods for engaging their communities. It is recommended that future research is conducted on defining factors of successful design and implementation groups and strategies in higher education.